

Solving the old and new social challenges through “The Democratization of Money”

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^a *PhiEconomy, a New Theory of Value for the CryptoEconomy & Post-Capitalism Era., Argentina*

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Robotization & artificial intelligence will wipe out 80% of current jobs. Climate change effects are having profound impact in the way we live and do business. United Nations and the World Bank have issued warnings in the last two years about the increase in poverty, inequality, unemployment. The World is changing dramatically and our system of belief is at risk or even our future as specie. We need a new center for our lives, different from the current notion of “work”. How Blockchain & the CryptoEconomy can help us to face this challenge?

2. Aim

Provide a new vision, a new way to think about our system...even about ourselves...based on the CryptoEconomy (Blockchain & Cryptocurrencies).

3. Material and methods

A research has been conducted by Alejandro Sewrjuign, in the last 5 years, analyzing the possibilities & capabilities of Blockchain & Cryptocurrencies applied to social behavior & social needs. Exploring the very nature of how a new decentralized system can impact the way we conduct businesses, the economy, our social relationships and, ultimately, ourselves as a specie. More than 150 books & publications -integrating subjects such as Philosophy, Sociology, Economy, Technology- were used for this investigation -starting from “On the Nature of Things” from Lucretius (50 B.C.E) to “Blockchain Revolution” from Don & Alex Tapscott (2016)-.

4. Results

With the unemployment growing faster due to automation, robotics, artificial intelligence and with 1.5 Billion of employed people living in extreme or moderated poverty (about 40% of total global working population), migrations happening around the World due to economic, climate and political challenges, it is time to re-think & revise the fundamentals of our social

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system: the notion of “work”, “profit” and even “capitalism” as we think of it today, should be modified. As a result, PhiEconomy provides a new economic framework, a new theory of value, to make possible an alternative, a new way to create bonds between humans at a global level, to gather & generate a new concept for “value” to our Society.

5. Conclusions

Distribution of resources & wealth at the Global Level, plus money issuing are the two main responsables or key factors for the main challenges we are facing (poverty, inequality, climate change and others).

Economic, Financial & Monetary policies are mere techniques or approximations to “value”, trying to mitigate “artificially” the fundamental problem provoking all of this: money is issued without something “real” sustaining it. It is totally disconnected from the value created by each human being. A company or a State alone will not be able to resolve this. We need a new global & decentralized system to drive a new concept for “value” -and the “Blockchain” as a concept can be the main driver- and “money” functioning as a reward -money being issued according to the value created by each person in real time, enabled by global platforms for transactions-. Internet had democratized the access to information, CryptoEconomy -Blockchain & Cryptocurrencies- can help us “democratize” the access to money at the global level and confront the global challenges successfully. A new type of Economy, focused & centered on people & purposes -an evolution of the triple impact notion: people, planet & profit-. This will enable us to find daily “purposes”, “occupations” and a new meaning of what value is for all of us. This is what PhiEconomy is all about, a “new theory of value” and the result of this work.

6. Keywords

Bitcoin; Blockchain; CryptoEconomy; Money; Democratization; Social; PhiEconomy

Author biography

Alejandro Mario Sewrjugin Alejandro Sewrjugin is a serial entrepreneur -25 years in the Tech sector-, speaker & philosopher. Recognized by INC Latinamerica Magazine in 2012 as one of the TOP 50 Entrepreneurs in Argentina of all times. Author of two books: “Understanding the Bitcoin: The Technology Transforming our World” and “Essential Principles on PhiEconomy: A Path to Abundance”. He works with organizations such as SAP, United Nations, Argentina’s National Government, Buenos Aires’s City Government, Singularity University, Endeavor to drive change through disruptive technologies. He holds a B.A degree from University of Buenos Aires and member of the Buenos Aires Economic Sciences Professional Organization.

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